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Designing Of Stadiums And Their Facilities With Respect To The Safety And Comfort Of People In South-South Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The present paper is on designing of stadiums and their facilities with respect to the safety and comfort of people the south-south Nigeria. A descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. The population of the study included both full-time and part-time staff of the case study stadiums. Taro Yamane formula was used to determine the sample size of the study where a total of 311 respondents were sampled randomly from a population of 1400 persons. The instrument for data collection was a structured 4-likert point questionnaire with a semi structured interview guide. Data analysis was carried out using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), version 20 and 2016 Microsoft Excel. The result of data analysis showed that since the mean score value for each of the items was higher than Three case study stadiums which were Godswill Akpabio stadium at Akwa Ibom State, Adokiye Amiesimaka Stadium at Rivers State and Stephen Keshi stadium at Delta State. Two research objectives and questions were stated for the study. The mean criterion mark of 2.50, they were all accepted. Thus, the stadium and its facilities are accessible by physically challenged people. It was recommended among others that the Day to day activities and maintenance of stadium safety and its facilities should be outsourced to expert Facilities Managers, to allow for overall sustenance of the facilities. The result of the data analysis showed that all the items tested above the mean criterion mark of 2.50, they were all accepted. Thus, a well-designed stadium and its facilities following internationally approved standards; do enhance the safety and comfort of people.

Keywords: stadiums, safety, designs, facilities

INTRODUCTION

Stadium is a place or venue for (mostly) outdoor sports, concerts, or other events and consists of a field or stage completely or partially surrounded by a tiered structure designed to allow spectators to stand or sit and view the event.^{[2][3]} Pausanias noted that for about half a century the only event at the ancient Greek Olympic festival was the race that comprised one length of the stadion at Olympia, where the word "stadium" originated.^[4] Most of the stadiums with a capacity of at least 10,000 are used for association football. Other popular stadium sports include gridiron football, baseball, cricket, the various codes

of rugby, field lacrosse, bandy, and bullfighting. Many large sports venues are also used for concerts. A notable Nigerian experience on the absence of safety measures in our stadiums was seen in March 2014, when a call for job interview into the Nigerian Immigration Service in Nigeria, saw various stadiums across the country which were being used as the test centre were overwhelmed by large crowd of people who turned up. A deadly stampede claimed the lives of several people, at stadiums in the Nigerian cities of Abuja, Benin and Port Harcourt, as well as a school in Mina city. (BBC News <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-africa-35690160>). In February 2019, another case happened at the Adokiye Amiesimaka Stadium Omagwa in River State during a political rally of the All Progressive Congress (APC) were at least 15 people died in a stampede at a campaign rally for Nigerian President Muhammadu Buhari. Most of the victims were reported to have fallen and been trampled on as the crowd tried to force its way through a partially locked gate to follow Mr Buhari as he left the arena. (BBC news <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-africa-47220825>). A stampede at the entrance of Godswill Akpabio International Stadium in Uyo, AkwaIbom in 2017, left many injured. The incident took place just before the match between the Super Eagles and the Chipolopo of Zambia as fans made their way into the stadium. The Akwa-Ibom stadium was filled beyond its capacity of 30,000. According to the PUNCH, some of the football fans were beaten with heavy sticks by soldiers at the gate of the stadium, resulting in a stampede as people sought to escape being hit. (The Cable <https://www.thecable.ng/stadium-stampede-several-injured-nigeria-zambia-match>). There have been very numerous incidents of stampedes at stadiums in different African nations. A case in which two people died at a high-profile football match at Johannesburg's Soccer City Stadium in South Africa following a stampede, while eight people were killed and almost 90 injured after a wall collapsed following a stampede at the DembaDiop stadium in Senegal. A football crowd in Malawi left eight people dead at the Bingu National Stadium in Lilongwe, while 17 fans died after hundreds of supporters stormed the gate at a venue in the city of Uige in Angola.(Stadium Business News <https://www.thestadiumbusiness.com/2017/10/10/nigerian-football-federation-denies-stadium-stampede-deaths/>). Although, these incidents have been drastically reduced in the developed countries, it is still a major issue in the developing and under developed countries of which Nigeria is one.

This research intends to examine the extent of safety measures put in place to manage stadiums in Nigeria using three stadiums in the South-South of Nigeria as case studies, and to propose the adoption of a management framework that incorporates both public and private owned stadiums.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

To examine the design of stadiums and its facilities with respect to standard safety measures.

Research Question

Do the design of stadiums and their facilities enhance the safety and comfort of people?

Significance of the Study

There is a dearth of literature on the assessment of proactive safety measures and procedures in sport facilities in Nigeria. This has led to different operational plan across these sport facilities. Every sport facility should have the same kind of operational procedure to ensure uniformity when an audit process is to be carried out. The lack of this uniformity has not given room to the creation of a proactive standard operational plan to govern sport facility management. Most of the reactive operational plan adopt the general safety procedure that is not specific to the sport industry but to other industry as well. Hence, the study will attempt to suggest better ways of managing sports facilities and stadiums in Nigeria; it will provide a guide for various stakeholders in the sporting environment on vital decisions to make in improving the management of their stadiums.

Scope of the Study

The scope of this study will be limited to stadiums in South-South, Nigeria(Rivers State, AkwaIbom State and Delta State).These stadiums were newly constructed in the twenty first century, and therefore form the basis for consideration and selection as a case study. They have often been used as host to the National team of Nigeria (Super Eagles) when they play their matches. The case study stadiums are

- i. Adokiye Amiesimaka stadium Omagwa, Rivers State
- ii. GodswillAkpabio Stadium Uyo, AkwaIbom State

iii. Stephen Keshi Stadium Asaba, Delta State.
Design and Safety of a Stadium

Plate 1: Design of A Stadium
 Source: LSU official site

The design of a stadium can promote safety or help management make better safety decisions. The design should take into cognizance several issues such as circulation (ingress, egress and emergency evacuation), fire safety, staircases, lifts, spectator accommodation (sitting and standing), communication system, first aid and medical provision etc. The safety of all those using a stadium must take priority over all other considerations in the design and management of the stadium, regardless of the level of funding available. The degree of luxury and comfort which can be built into a stadium will depend on the amount of money available but the fundamental requirement which must be met, regardless of available funding levels, is that the stadium must be a safe and secure facility for all those who use it, whether they are spectators, match participants, officials, media personnel, staff or others. Even before the basic planning begins, it should be clearly understood by the prospective owners and by those concerned in the planning, designing, construction and management processes that human safety will be the first and foremost priority. It will be a condition that may not, under any circumstances, be put aside or circumvented in order to accommodate other requirements. (FIFA, TRR, 2007).

Stadium Location

According to the FIFA Technical Report (2007) stadium should be situated in a location which is sufficiently large to provide spacious and safe external public circulation/activity areas and marshalling space for service vehicles and functions. While it is normal for the arrival of spectators at the stadium to be spread over a sufficiently lengthy period to prevent undue congestion near the turnstiles, the majority of spectators will seek to leave the stadium at the same time, resulting in significant space requirements. The availability of sufficient external space will also allow for future extension or redevelopment. Many famous stadiums around the world are in heavily developed locations with roads, buildings and canals

immediately adjacent on all sides. Their renovation and redevelopment possibilities are restricted by their limited site size and this is not a desirable situation. Large sites reduce the probability that the site may have to be abandoned in the long term, or even in the short term, because of its inability to accommodate some unforeseen development requirement. Larger sites also increase the possibility of providing adequate on-site parking areas— a requirement which will probably remain for the foreseeable future.

As a site becomes more suburban and isolated from public transport, it will have to become larger to accommodate the required additional parking. In this situation, convenient and multiple access to major roads and motorways is essential. In an ideal world, the ultimate location would probably be a large city-centre site with good access to public transport, major roads and motorways and parking that can be used by others when games are not being played. This reduces the possibility that large parking areas will be used for as little as 100 to 200 hours per year. A stadium with ambitions to host international events is more attractive to event holders if it is within comfortable reach of hotels and active commercial environments and at least one international airport.

Plate 2: Electronic counting turnstile gate
Source: Alamy

Entrance and Exit Routes

The templates made provisions that public passageways and stairways in the spectator areas should be clearly marked, as should all gates leading from the spectator areas into the playing area and all exit doors and gates leading out of the stadium. All public passageways, corridors, stairs, doors and gates must be kept free of any obstructions that could impede the free flow of spectators. Exit doors and gates in the stadium and all gates leading from the spectator areas into the playing area must open outwards, away

from the spectators. They must remain unlocked while spectators are in the stadium. However, to prevent illegal entry or intrusion on non-match days, they may be fitted with a locking device which can be operated simply and quickly by anyone inside. Each of these doors and gates must be attended at all times by a specially appointed steward, to guard against abuse and to ensure immediate escape routes in the event of an emergency evacuation. Under no circumstances must they be locked with a key during the time that spectators are in the stadium. *FIFA, TRR (2007). LMC 2014/2015.*

The design and management of entrance and exit routes is most important to the survival of the spectators in an event. In most events in stadiums in Nigeria, people enter the stadiums and exit through the same route. It could be very frustrating most times to force your way against the tide of people moving the opposite direction. It throws a big doubt whether officials have any safety manual or have looked at these templates. It was noticed by observation on match days in the case stadiums that this instruction as laid down in the various evaluating template are not adhered to, as locking of gates during events or match days in the stadium have proved unsafe.. This has most times proved to be very unwise and fatal, especially in the event of any emergencies in the stadium, this could cause a stampede, as many would rush to the gates opened.

In the UK, most of the stadiums have properly labeled exit and entrance routes. The Green Guide outlined several points as stated below: Amongst others, the design should take into consideration the following:

- a. Entrances to each part of the ground should, wherever practicable, be designed and located so as to allow for the even distribution of spectators and to prevent local pressure building up outside the ground.
- b. Walls, fences and gates should not provide the opportunity for hand or foot-holds which might assist climbing. They should be regularly inspected.
- c. The installation of closed circuit television should be considered in order to assist in the monitoring of crowd densities outside the ground and throughout the ingress/egress routes
- d. The design of the turnstile and its housing should allow for the operator to see and communicate clearly with entrants.
- e. Turnstiles are not suitable for use by wheelchair users, visually impaired spectators and people with assistance dogs. The most practical design solution is to provide level access via a gate or door, with an appropriate vision panel, which is staffed by a steward. Arrangements must be in place to ensure that all those entering by such routes are counted among the spectators attending the event.
- f. Entrances should be sited so that the flow of people from them to the spectator accommodation is, as far as possible, evenly distributed. Where this distribution is uneven and gives rise to congestion at an entrance, consideration should be given to changing the turnstile or entry point arrangements, and if possible, to directing more people to under-used entrances. Additional measures might include improved signposting and increased stewarding, both inside and outside the ground.
- g. Entry routes should not be obstructed. Amenities such as refreshment kiosks or toilets should be located away from the immediate area of the turnstiles and entry routes.
- h. Entry and exit routes are often common to each other and in such cases the considerations which apply to exit routes therefore apply also to entry routes. (The Green Guide)

Staircase

Staircase provides access & communication between floors in storey buildings. Therefore, Management and designers should consider all aspects of safety while designing a staircase. The disposition, design and management of stairways, ramps, lifts and escalators at sports grounds should be such as to provide smooth and unimpeded circulation for spectators under all conditions. Movement on stairways, especially downward movement, poses a considerable potential risk to crowds both in normal circumstances, such as at the end of an event, or in an emergency. The effects of stumbling, pushing, jostling and congestion are potentially dangerous if, as a result, the crowd suddenly surges forward or if, for any reason, any individuals suddenly change direction. In order to minimise hazards the design of stairways should

comply with all the relevant requirements of internationally standard Building Regulations.(The Green Guide)

Passenger lifts

A passenger lift is the most suitable means of vertical access for disabled people and should be provided wherever possible. Wheelchair users and other spectators with impaired mobility need sufficient time and space to manoeuvre into the lift and should be able to reach the controls on the landing, and also in the car itself. Sufficient space should be provided in front of lifts so that people waiting for them will not obstruct crowd flows. It is important to note that the design of a passenger lift may determine whether it may be used in the event of an emergency evacuation. Consideration should be given to the size of lifts where the medical plan provides for their use to transport injured spectators on stretchers. In addition to passenger lifts, internal stairs should always be provided as an alternative means of vertical access, designed to suit ambulant disabled people and those with impaired vision. (The Green Guide)

Escalators

Plate 3: Escalators

Source: Dan Walker (2015)

Escalators are not a suitable means of vertical access for all disabled people. Therefore, wherever an escalator is installed between floors, a clearly signposted alternative access by lift should be provided. Although escalators may form an integral part of the entry and exit systems at certain sports grounds, they should not be used for the purposes of calculating the emergency evacuation capacity. Escalators should discharge into a space sufficiently large and clear to avoid people being unable to step off the escalator in congested situations. Consideration should also be given to the possible consequences of any breakdowns, particularly of one flight within a series of multiple level escalators. It may be necessary to provide alternative exit routes leading from the escalators landings to staircases or large safe areas, in order to avoid crowd build up on landings in the case of breakdowns. (The Green Guide)

Plate 3: The Emirates Stadium
Source, bleacherreport.com

METHODOLOGY

The study utilized the descriptive research design. Rivers State, also known simply as Rivers, is one of the 36 states of Nigeria. Rivers state currently has three stadiums (Sharks Stadium located at Port Harcourt township metropolis, Yakubu Gowon Stadium located at Elekahia and AdokiyeAmiesimaka Stadium located at Omagwa. Akwa Ibom is a state in Nigeria. It is located in the coastal southern part of the country, lying between latitudes 4°32'N and 5°33'N, and longitudes 7°25'E and 8°25'E. The state is located in the South-South geopolitical zone, and is bordered on the east by Cross River State, on the west by Rivers State and Abia State, and on the south by the Atlantic Ocean and the southernmost tip of Cross River State. Delta State (created on August 27, 1991) is an oil and agricultural producing state in Nigeria. It is situated in the region known as the South-South geo-political zone with a population of 4,112,445. The capital city is Asaba, located at the northern end of the state, with an estimated area of 762 square kilometres (294 sq mi), while Warri is the economic nerve center of the state and also the most populated. It is located in the southern end of the state. The population for the study covered the staff (both full time and part time) that performed different functions and roles in the case study stadiums across the study areas. The population across the three-case study stadiums was at one thousand four hundred (1400) staff (full time and part time staff). Using large samples from different stadiums (Public and Private) would have been appropriate for this research, but because of insufficient funds and the security challenges in the country, I have narrowed it down to three (3) case studies. This will in no form reduce the quality of the research as the case studies tend to provide answers to the research questions and could also stand as a standard in stadium management. Researchers require academic and professional experts to edit their questionnaires before a survey can be carried out (Umeh, 2018). According to Devellis as cited by Mugenda, (2004) reliability is the proportion of variance attributable to the time measurement of a

variable and estimates the consistency of such measurement over time from a research instrument. It is a measure of the degree to which a research instrument would yield the same results or data after repeated trials. The researcher carried out a face-to-face questionnaire administration to the respondents in the selected stadiums. The researcher solicited for the assistance of the facility manager to assist him in informing the staff and administer the questionnaires to them. Both quantitative and qualitative methods were employed in the data analysis. For quantitative aspects; Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) and excel, frequency distributions, percentages and descriptive analysis of the safety measures in managing stadiums. Data collected was collated and analyzed using various quantitative statistical models such as bar chart and pie chart. Each data was examined and analyzed on its merit and grouped into the various aspects of information requirement for the purpose of this research work. The findings were critically examined again to make sure that they are not incongruous with the research objectives. Mean and the standard deviation were used to analyze the research questions posed for the study. A mean score of 2.50 was the benchmark for acceptance.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Data Presentation

Demographic Data

a. Gender and Age of Respondents

Table 1: Crosstabulation between Gender and Stadium

		Stadium			Total
		AdokiyeAmiesimaka Stadium	GodswillAkpabio Stadium	Stephen Keshi Stadium	
Gender	Female	34	37	35	133
	Male	71	67	62	173
Total		105	104	97	306

Table 4.1 displays the cross-tabulation between gender of the respondents across the case study stadiums. Adokiye Amiesimaka stadium had a total of 105 respondents where 34 and 71 respondents were female and male respectively. Godswill Akpabio stadium had a total of 104 respondents where 37 and 67 were females and males respectively. Stephen Keshi stadium had a total of 97 respondents where 35 and 62 were females and males respectively.

Table 2: Cross-tabulation between Gender and Age

		Age			Total
		25 – 31 Years	32 – 38 Years	39 – 45 Years	
Gender	Female	39	68	26	133
	Male	40	85	48	173
Total		79	153	74	306

Table 2 shows the cross-tabulation of gender against the age ranges of the respondents. For ages between 25-31 years, there were 39 females and 40 males. For ages between 32-38 years, there were 68 females and 85 males. For ages between 39-45 years, there were 26 females and 48 males. Thus, giving a total of 306 where 133 were females and 173 were males.

Figure 2: A Bar Chart Representation of Gender and Years of Experience

Figure 3: A Bar Chart Representation of Type of Staff and Stadium

Research Questions

Research Question: Does the design of stadium and its facilities enhance the safety and comfort of people?

Table 3: Walkway Safety Designs

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Remark
1	Slip-resistant materials install at all edges, with clear, visible markings on landings	93	188	25	0	3.22	Accepted
2	Guardrails and handrails are designed around the "average" range of people's heights, weights, and centers of mass	197	119	0	0	3.74	Accepted
3	Exit paths are properly sized and identified with signage	233	73	0	0	3.76	Accepted
4	Wet areas are installed with slip-resistant materials with proper lighting and drainage	127	118	49	12	3.18	Accepted
5	Labels are fit tightly on railings and other surfaces	199	94	13	0	3.61	Accepted
6	Every doorway or passage that might be mistaken for an exit marked "NOT AN EXIT" with an indication of its actual use	236	70	0	0	3.77	Accepted

In table 4.3, the walk safety design of the stadium were measured. Six items were developed to elicit responses. All the item tested above the mean criterion mark of 2.50 and they were accepted.

Item 1 assessed if slip-resistant materials were installed at all edges, with clear, visible markings on landings and it had a mean score value of 3.22. Item 2 determined if guardrails and handrails are designed around the "average" range of people's heights, weights, and centers of mass and it had a mean score value of 3.74. Item 3 measured if the exit paths are properly sized and identified with signage and it had a mean score value of 3.76. Item 4 sought to know if wet areas are installed with slip-resistant materials with proper lighting and drainage and it had a mean score value of 3.18. Item 5 assessed if labels are fit tightly on railings and other surfaces and it had a mean score value of 3.61. Item 6 determined if every doorway or passage that might be mistaken for an exit marked "NOT AN EXIT" with an indication of its actual use and it had a mean score value of 3.77. Since each of these items tested above the mean criterion mark of 2.50, they were all accepted.

Table 4: Seating Safety Designs

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Remark
1	For every row of seats that is more than 10 seats there are Aisles on both side	152	154	0	0	3.50	Accepted
2	There are no more than 42 seats between aisles	173	110	23	0	3.49	Accepted
3	Steps within aisles are full width of the aisle with a minimum aisle width of 1 metre	174	132	0	0	3.57	Accepted
4	The clearance between rows of seats is 500 mm	162	144	0	0	3.53	Accepted
5	The aisles and the tread of each step is usually illuminated whenever the venue is open to the public	150	156	0	0	3.49	Accepted
6	The aisle lighting is connected to the emergency lighting so that in the event of the aisle lighting failing, the emergency lighting is automatically energized	164	142	0	0	3.54	Accepted
7	All seats are securely fixed to the floor	257	49	0	0	3.84	Accepted

As shown in table 4, seven items were designed to measure the stadium seating safety designs and all the items tested above the mean criterion mark of 2.50. Item 1 measured if for every row of seats that is more than 10 seats there are Aisles on both side and it had a mean score value of 3.50. Item 2 assessed if there are no more than 42 seats between aisles and it had a mean score value of 3.49. Item 3 sought to know if the steps within aisles are full width of the aisle with a minimum aisle width of 1 metre and it had a mean

score value of 3.57. Item 4 determined if the clearance between rows of seats is 500 mm and it had a mean score value of 3.53. Item 5 ascertained if the aisles and the tread of each step is usually illuminated whenever the venue is open to the public and it had a mean score value of 3.49. Item 6 measured if the aisle lighting is connected to the emergency lighting so that in the event of the aisle lighting failing, the emergency lighting is automatically energized and it had a mean score value of 3.54. Item 7 determined if all seats are securely fixed to the floor and it had a mean score value of 3.84. Since all the items tested above the mean score value of 2.50, they were all accepted.

Table 5: Fire Hazard Indices

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Remark
1	Materials used in the seats do have a spread of flame index of 0 and a smoke developed index of not more than 5	188	118	0	0	3.61	Accepted
2	Materials for ceiling finish, lining surface or attachment do have a spread of flame index of no more than 6 and a smoke developed index of no more than 3.	188	118	0	0	3.61	Accepted
3	Materials for wall finish, lining, surface or attachment do have a spread of flame index of no more than 6 and a smoke developed index of no more than 5.	221	85	0	0	3.72	Accepted
4	Materials for floor finish, lining surface or attachment do have a spread of flame index of no more than 7 and a smoke developed index of no more than 5.	246	60	0	0	3.80	Accepted
5	There is a functional occupant notification system such as fire alarm system component such as a bell, horn, speaker, light, or text display that provides audible, tactile, or visible outputs, etc. in the facility.	191	83	13	11	3.43	Accepted

In table 5, the fire hazard indices for the stadium were measured. Five items were designed for the measurement and they are tested above the mean criterion mark of 2.50. while Item 1 measured the materials used in the seats do have a spread of flame index of 0 and a smoke developed index of not more than 5, Item 2 determined if the materials for ceiling finish, lining surface or attachment do have a spread of flame index of no more than 6 and a smoke developed index of no more than 3 and they both had a mean score value of 3.61. Item 3 ascertained if materials for wall finish, lining, surface or attachment do have a spread of flame index of no more than 6 and a smoke developed index of no more than 5 and it had a mean score value of 3.72. Item 4 sought to know if materials for floor finish, lining surface or attachment do have a spread of flame index of no more than 7 and a smoke developed index of no more than 5 and it had a mean score value of 3.80. item 5 measured if there is a functional occupant notification system such as fire alarm system component such as a bell, horn, speaker, light, or text display that provides audible, tactile, or visible outputs, etc. in the facility and it had a mean score value of 3.43. Since all the items tested above the mean criterion mark of 2.50, they were all accepted. Thus, a well-designed stadium and its facilities following internationally approved standards, do enhance the safety and comfort of people.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

On if the design of stadium and its facilities enhance the safety and comfort of people, findings showed that the design of the stadium along with its facilities were made to enhance safety and comfort for the people who would use it. However, these facilities may not ensure safety and comfort if they are not adequately maintained. For instance, a visit to Adokiye stadium in Port Harcourt, the researcher observed that some part of the receptacle was leaking which could have been a source of discomfort if an event was to be holding when rain was falling. This is an indication that the receptacle is due for maintenance. During a visit to Godswill Akpabio stadium, the facility manager mentioned that,

the facility has a routine inspection cycle by the facility management team on a fortnightly basis to check for possible faults. Detected faults are then sent in form of an official memo requesting for a routine maintenance to be carried out on the facility (Respondent 1).

He further added that,

The nature of the routine maintenance is dependent on the extent of the detected fault in the facility (Respondent 1).

In Stephen Keshi stadium, the facility undergoes a routine daily maintenance since it is directly managed by the State Government. Civil servants are directly assigned to clean up the facility as their civil service job roles. The effectiveness of this routine maintenance done by the staff is not adequate as the researcher observed a nonchalant approach towards their job roles. The cleaning was not effective as such was not sustainable. Speaking with one of the Sport Commission management team on how effective has the maintenance of the facility been since it was being managed by the government of the state under their commission. He retorted that;

the maintenance policy governing the facility has not been fully implemented as funds meant for full implementation are usually diverted to individual pockets. More so, most people working in the commission came here based on referrals and most of them do not follow laid down routine maintenance process (Respondent 2).

He further stated that,

The issue is the enacting the maintenance policy but implementing it. The issue of shared interest in government funds meant for the facility routine maintenance has affected how effective the routine maintenance of the facility can be (Respondent 2).

Another staff of the Sport Commission assert that,

Although, budgetary allocations are made yearly for statutory maintenance of the facility which are usually outsourced to a competent firm while being supervised by the management team of the Sport Commission. Most times the statutory maintenance is not effective as the budgeted funds get siphoned in bits till a lean some amount gets to the contracted firm mandated to carry out the statutory maintenance (Respondents 3).

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

This study was on the examination of the safety measures in the management of stadium facilities in the south-south Nigeria, using three case study stadiums which were Godswill Akpabio stadium at Akwa Ibom State, Adokiye Amiesimaka Stadium at Rivers State and Stephen Keshi stadium at Delta State. A research objective and question were stated for the study. A descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. The population of the study included both full-time and part-time staff of the case study stadiums. Taro Yamane formula was used to determine the sample size of the study where a total of 311 respondents were sampled randomly from a population of 1400 persons. The instrument for data collection was a structured 4-likert point questionnaire with a semi structured interview guide. Data analysis was carried out using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), version 20 and 2016 Microsoft Excel. The analysis was done using frequency distributions, percentages and descriptive analysis of safety indicators as a tool in managing stadiums. Mean and the standard deviation were used to analyze the research questions posed for the study. A mean score of 2.50 was the benchmark for acceptance. Findings showed that the safety measures available in each stadium were adequate but the method of administering and managing these measures were not reliable. Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that there is no safety guide published to regulate the management stadium. Also, in Nigeria, most of the public owned stadiums are controlled and managed by the various state governments.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The researcher made the following recommendations for the study;

- i. Institutions that should be responsible for the regulating and monitoring of safety of stadiums and its facilities should be set up.
2. These institutions should be tasked with the responsibility amongst others, to carry out a thorough assessment of the safety of stadiums and their facilities and also issue a safety certificate if deemed safe, before the commencement of any event in the stadium.
3. Every stadium should have an In-House Management or Ground Management that should be responsible for the safety of spectators in the stadium.

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